

Be the first to discover:

Diseased species + **Cause** + **Sample** + **Biomarker**

MOVES AND GUESSES

- Enter another species' cage → make a guess.
- Enter your own cage → roll the dice again.
- If you don't receive a card → you can make a new guess or roll the dice again.

BIOMARKERS

- Magnifying glass colour → species to which the biomarker belongs.
- White magnifying glass → see the biomarker of any species.
- If you already know that biomarker → draw a random card from that player.

BIOSENSOR

- For 2 rounds → you only need to pass by the magnifying glasses to collect the biomarkers.
- At the end → leave it at the space you're in.

FUNCTIONAL DIETS

- Draw a random card from another player, write it down and return it.
- Cures parasites and cross-contamination.

AQLUA

SPECIAL CARDS

- Vaccine and strategic interference cards → kept secret (max. 2 cards). Can be played at any time.
- Boat → use it to go anywhere. Can be stolen for crossing.
- Other cards → read and apply immediately or on your turn.

UNDERWATER TUNNEL

- Free passage shrimp ↔ salmon.
- One-way → direction changes every time someone passes by the laboratory.
- Counts as one space.

Final guess: Go to the laboratory. No exact number needed on the dice. Using the boat, you can move there directly.